

N-DeciMa: Neurophysiological bases of decision-making processes: dissociating risk and uncertainty in the human brain

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Creators: Yulia Karimova, Mafalda Lopes, Catarina Botelho, Tiago Paiva

Affiliation: INESC TEC, Nursing School of Porto (ESEP), FPCEUP

ORCID iD:

Yulia Karimova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1015-6709>,

Mafalda Lopes <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6157-7821>

Catarina Botelho <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9209-2077>

Tiago Paiva <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5461-6802>

Project abstract: Humans face a daily variety of decision-making challenges in distinct aspects of life [1]. Most of these decisions are made under uncertainty, a concept employed to describe an imperfect knowledge about the expected outcomes for distinct choices [2]. Although the conceptual distinction between uncertainty and risk was formulated in the early 1920s by Frank Knight [3], the distinction is not always clearly stated in the neuroscientific study of decision-making, leading to an often-interchangeable misuse of the concepts of risk and uncertainty. Nonetheless, research in neuroscience has provided evidence for the dissociation of the neuronal underpinnings of decision-making in situations of risk and uncertainty, pointing towards the recruitment of distinct mechanisms in processing risk and uncertainty: risk has been mainly associated with increased activation in brain regions typically associated with cognitive and attentional processes, and uncertainty has been associated with brain regions usually related to emotional reactivity (e.g., [4,5]). Most existing studies on the neuronal underpinnings of risk and uncertainty processing in decision making rely on the functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) technique. The fMRI offers high spatial resolution in the study of the recruited brain regions, but lacks the temporal precision required to disentangle the distinct processes related with risk and uncertainty processing. In order to overcome the existing limitations in the literature and shed light on the temporal brain dynamics of risk and uncertainty processing while controlling for methodological confounds, we propose a research plan that aims to: (a) experimentally dissociate the neuronal correlates of risk and uncertainty processing in decision-making, while controlling for expected value and utility; and to (b) provide a multilevel assessment of risk and uncertainty processing, complementing behavioral data with neurophysiological correlates of the autonomic and central nervous systems. In the context of the present research plan, two related studies are proposed.

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1. Output summary (Data collection)

This project is divided into 2 studies with different types of data, collecting methods and management rules, and each study has Pilot studies to test procedure. This project is financed by the BIAL (Grant Number:PT/FB/BL-2020-252), and responds to all existing requirements related to the RDM and Protection of Personal Data This project is financed by the BIAL Foundation (Grant Number:PT/FB/BL-2020-252), and responds to all existing requirements related to the RDM and Protection of Personal Data, as assessed by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto (https://sigarra.up.pt/fpceup/pt/p/comissao_etica). All members of the project follow the established, updated and monitored Data Management Plan during the development of the work and after its finalization.

Collected data during this project is important and aims to answer to:

- experimentally dissociate the neuronal correlates of risk and uncertainty processing in decision-making, while controlling for expected value and utility;
- provide a multilevel assessment of risk and uncertainty processing, complementing behavioural data with neurophysiological correlates.

Pilot study of Study 1:

Participants: The pilot sample will consist of 4 adult participants recruited from the community (2 female). All participants will have normal hearing, normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity, and no history of psychiatric nor neurological disorders, or drug abuse.

Materials: the materials will include a short sociodemographic questionnaire, the translated and adapted versions of the Domain-specific Risk-attitude Scale [6], the short form of the Intolerance of Uncertainty Scale [7,8], and the decision-making task under risk vs uncertainty.

Methodology: After signing the informed consent, participants will be placed in a data collection chamber. While seated, the ECG electrodes will be placed in accordance with the Lead II of the Einthoven triangle [9]. Then participants will be instructed on the trial structure of the decision-making task and will be told that the goal of the task is to accumulate the most possible money from the bets. Before the beginning of the task, ECG will be recorded at rest for 60 seconds. Each participant will then play 180 trials of the decision-making task, corresponding to 15 bets on each level of the factors manipulated in the task: goal of the bet (2 levels – gain and loss avoidance), size of the bet (3 levels – low, medium, and high), and context of the bet (2 levels – risk and uncertainty). After the decision-making task, the participant will complete the self-report measures of risk and uncertainty. All procedures are expected to last 90 minutes and each participant will receive a 15€ gift card as compensation for their time and contribution.

Study 1 - Assessing preferences under risk vs uncertainty: self-report, behavioral, and autonomic nervous system data:

Will explore the association between self-report measures of attitudes towards risk and uncertainty, and the behavioral and autonomic nervous system correlates of risk and uncertainty processing in decision making. A sample of 80 adult individuals recruited from the community will engage in the study. Self-report measures of attitudes towards risk and uncertainty will be assessed using The Domain-specific Risk-attitude Scale (DRaS;[6]), adapted for European Portuguese and the short form of the Intolerance of Uncertainty Scale (IUS; [7,8]), also adapted for European Portuguese respectively. In order to assess how risk and uncertainty affect decision-making and its neurophysiological correlates, an experimental decision-making task is proposed, which allows the parametric manipulation of both risk and uncertainty independently from confounding variables such as expected value and utility. Electrocardiographic (ECG) activity will be recorded during this task.

Participants: The study sample will consist of 80 adult participants recruited from the community (40 female). All participants will have normal hearing, normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity, and no history of psychiatric nor neurological disorders, or drug abuse.

Materials: the materials will include a short sociodemographic questionnaire, the translated and adapted versions of the Domain-specific Risk-attitude Scale [6], the short form of the Intolerance of Uncertainty Scale [7,8], and the decision-making task under risk vs uncertainty.

Decision-making task under risk vs. uncertainty: on each trial, there are two phases where cards are drawn (without replacement within each trial) from a deck of 10, numbered from 1 to 10. Before the first draw, subjects must place a bet with variable size on two options: "second card higher" or "lower" (then the first card shown). After bet placement, the context of the bet (risk vs. uncertainty) will be manipulated in the first card drawn. In risk trials, one card will be drawn at this stage. In uncertainty trials, more than one card will be drawn at the same time (in the first draw) and subjects will be told that the selected card is one of the cards drawn (never knowing each one) - thus, uncertainty increases with the number of cards that are drawn at this stage varying from low uncertainty (two cards) to high uncertainty (eight cards) and is independent of risk. Upon the first draw, a decision stage is included allowing to weigh the expected utility associated with variations in risk and uncertainty. Here participants must decide if they want to maintain the initial bet amount, reduce the bet down to a minimum of 50% of the initial bet or increase the bet up to a maximum of 50% of the initial bet. After the decision stage, the second card is drawn, and the result of the bet is presented to the participant that could either win the bet or not in the gain conditions or avoid loss or lose in loss-avoidance conditions.

Methodology: During this study participants will fill self-report measures of risk and uncertainty, carrying out decision-making tasks based on the card selection game with definition if

the "second card higher" or "lower". All activities that include participants will be started after signing of the informed consent. During the decision-making task, ECG will be continuously recorded using a BIOPAC MP36 system (BIOPAC Systems, Inc.). The ECG signal will be subjected to a standard pre-processing pipeline and analyzed for heart-rate frequency and variability in the distinct trials of the experimental task. The data collection will be individual and at the laboratory's data-collection chamber.

RAW data (a database with data collected by the application of the scales):

- **Scales assessment data** - a self-report, behavioural, and also a psychophysiological characterization of individual decisions under risk vs uncertainty.

Self-report measures of risk and uncertainty:

The Domain-specific Risk-attitude Scale (DRaS; [6]) is a 30-item scale that assesses individual propensity for risk taking in five domains: financial decisions (both gambling and financial), health/safety, recreational, ethical, and social decisions. Respondents rate on a 7-point Likert scale the likelihood of engaging in domain-specific risky activities, their own perception of the magnitude of the risks, and the expected benefits of those activities. The DRaS provides an individual score for risk-taking, risk perception, and value attribution in each domain.

The short form of the **Intolerance of Uncertainty Scale (IUS; [7,8])** is a 27-item scale that assesses reactions to uncertainty, ambiguous situations, and to the future. Items are scored on a 5-point Likert scale. The IUS is assumed as a unidimensional scale yielding an individual score for global intolerance to uncertainty.

Processed data: Self reported data from DRaS - total and domain specific individual scores (financial decisions - both gambling and financial, health/safety, recreational, ethical, and social decisions) of propensity towards risk-taking; and IUS - total score of intolerance towards uncertainty; will be stored in excel files and processed in IBM SPSS Statistics software (generating SPSS files with processed data). ECG data will be processed in MATLAB.

Software used: MP36 Data Acquisition Systems (BIOPAC) for ECG data collection, E-Prime license for stimulus presentation, MATLAB licenses for data analysis.

The main variables will be: Self-reported attitudes towards risk and uncertainty, self-reported psychopathic traits - TriPM, SRP-SH; mean heart rate (HR), Standard Deviations of NN Intervals (SDNN), the Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD).

Pilot study of Study 2: test the procedure and the communication between the stimulation unit and the EEG recording system during the decision-making task. The pilot study will also focus on the feature's extraction from the EEG signal.

Participants: The pilot sample will consist of 4 adult participants recruited from the community (2 female). All participants will have normal hearing, normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity, and no history of psychiatric nor neurological disorders, or drug abuse.

Materials: the materials will include a small sociodemographic questionnaire, and the decision-making task (the same described for study 1).

Methodology: After signing the informed consent, the participant will be placed in a data-collection chamber. While seated, the 128-channels EEG sensor net (Electrical Geodesics Inc.) will be placed in the participant's head. Each participant will be instructed on the trial structure of the decision-making task and will be told that goal of the task is to accumulate the most possible money from the initial bets. Before the beginning of the task, a resting-state EEG period will be recorded (3 minutes of eyes open and eyes closed). The participant will then play 240 trials of the decision-making task, corresponding to 20 bets on each level of the factors manipulated in the task, ensuring a good signal-to-noise ratio in the ERP data. All procedures are expected to last 90 minutes and each participant will receive a 15€ gift card as compensation for their time and contribution.

Study 2 - The temporal central brain dynamics of risk vs uncertainty processing:

Will focus on EEG and Event Related Potentials (ERP) correlates of risk and uncertainty processing. The analysis will be focused on the cue-related reward positivity (cue-RewP) and cue-P3 ERP components as correlates of distinct processes for risk and uncertainty processing (Software EEGLAB - MATLAB). Additional exploratory analysis on the functional connectivity of the EEG network in response to risk and uncertainty variations will be conducted. Taken together both studies provide the necessary data for a comprehensive multi-level assessment of the brain temporal dynamics underlying risk and uncertainty processing. This study includes Pilot study before the principal activities.

Participants: The same sample of 80 adult individuals will also engage in study 2, and will participate in a **second data collection session**, at least 6 months apart from the first one. All participants will have normal hearing, normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity, and no history of psychiatric nor neurological disorders, or drug abuse.

Materials: the materials will include a small sociodemographic questionnaire, and the decision-making task (the same described for study 1).

Methodology: After signing the informed consent, the participant will be placed in a data collection chamber. While seated, the 128-channels EEG sensor net (Electrical Geodesics Inc.) will be placed in the participant's head. Each participant will be instructed on the trial structure of the decision-making task and will be told that goal of the task is to accumulate the most possible money from the initial bets. Before the beginning of the task, a resting-state EEG period will be recorded (3 minutes of eyes open and eyes closed). The participant will then play 240 trials of the

decision-making task, corresponding to 20 bets on each level of the factors manipulated in the task, ensuring a good signal-to-noise ratio in the ERP data. All procedures are expected to last 90 minutes and each participant will receive a 15€ gift card as compensation for their time and contribution.

RAW data (a database with data collected by the application of the scales)

- EEG data collection; data related to analysis of the risks and uncertainty; excel files; measures; self-reports, behavioural decision-making reports.

Processed data: EEG data (processed in EEGlab - Matlab), that will be published after the project conclusion and after the publishing of the papers related to the data.

Software used: High density (128-channel) EEG system, 1 * NetAmps 300, 6 * EEG 128-electrode caps - Electrical Geodesic's Inc., E-Prime license for stimulus presentation, EEGLAB-MATLAB licenses for data analysis.

The main variables will be: cue-RewP and cue-P3 event-related potentials; IUS (uncertainty intolerance) and DRaS (domain-specific risk attitudes) scores, and psychopathic traits measures (TriPM, SRP-SH).

Sociodemographic variables: age, gender, nationality, native language, employment status, level of education, laterality, visual and auditory acuity, mental health and neurological history, medication, substances use (drugs, alcohol); quality and number of hours slept before the data collection, recent alterations in daily routine.

Information about data can be seen in Table 1, which will be updated during the project:

Type	Instrument for collecting	Data Owner	Storage	License/ Restriction	Expected format and size
dataset1 XX_name_data_version			Zenodo and RDM INESC TEC (https://rdm.inesctec.pt/)	CC-BY-SA 4.0	
sensitive data			Not publicly available.		
private data			Not publicly available.		
confidential documents			Not publicly available.	Non-Disclosure Agreements	
other types of data					

2. Responsibilities

Supervisors of the project: Tiago Paiva

Research team: Fernando Barbosa, Fernando Ferreira-Santos, Carina Fernandes, João Marques Teixeira, Rita Pasion, Carlos Seixas, Carlos Campos, Catarina Botelho

Responsible entity: Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto (FPCEUP)

Responsible for the collection, data analysis, processing and preservation data: Tiago Paiva

Others Researchers of the Project with access to the data RAW: Catarina Botelho

Responsible for publishing and sharing data:

Responsible for DMP creation, update and monitoring: Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com); Mafalda Lopes (mafalda@fpce.up.pt); Tiago Paiva (tiagopaiva@fpce.up.pt); Catarina Botelho (catarinabotelho@fpce.up.pt).

All partners and members of the project need to agree with the created DMP and the rules defined therein. The DMP will be created according to the recommendations of the BIAL, which in turn, follows RDM and GDPR requirements, such as open-science and FAIR principles.

3. FAIR data

1. Findability

To ensure that the data is findable it will be described according to the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) (<https://ddialliance.org/>) that is an international standard aimed at describing data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioral, economic, and health sciences, and the Dublin Core (DC) that is a metadata standard aimed at describing digital objects (<http://dublincore.org/>).

The processed data will be deposited on the data repository that allows the DOI assignment (it will be defined later). Each published dataset of the project will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned by the chosen research data repository to make datasets more findable, accessible and reusable by others. Only anonymized data will be available during and after the end of the project. No sensitive and personal data will be stored longer than necessary to conduct the project effectively or used for any other purposes. Data with sensitive or personal information will be deleted as soon as possible - until then, it will be stored in Laboratory PC of Tiago Paiva.

More information about these data will be added on the next version of DMP. Nonetheless, subjects have the right to ask for the exclusion of their collected data at any time.

Information related to version control will also be added later on the next version. The DMP will be published on the Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be seen as the output of the project.

2. Accessibility

The RAW data of both studies will only be accessible to Tiago Paiva and Catarina Botelho, and will be destroyed as soon as possible after transcripts or processing. The RAW data will be stored on the Laboratory PC, and on the laboratory's online cloud storage (NAS). While processing data, RAW data may be stored in the computers of Tiago Paiva and Catarina Botelho.

The EEG will be accessible to Tiago Paiva, and destroyed after their processing (RAW data that can include any sensitive and personal information).

The processed data will be open without any restrictions on the data repository (OSF - Open Science Framework) with DOI assignment, but only after publishing the respective papers (embargo period). Moreover, they will be stored on the laboratory PC of Tiago for 5 years after the conclusion of the project. Moreover, processed data from all the studies (and without any sensitive and personal information) will be made available to all researchers who wish to learn about the methodology used and/or replicate these studies in another population, through an Open Science platform (e.g. Open Science Framework; www.osf.io); the provided data will have all the information needed to prevent misinterpretations or its incorrect use; this will be defined with more detail, in a later DMP version.

Scales assessment answers will be stored as Excel files for statistical processing (processed and anonymized). Only the members of the research team will have access to these files.

All collected data will be stored and retained only for the necessary period to fulfill the purposes for which they were collected and processed, namely scientific research and publishing.

The processed data (datasets) of the project may be published in scientific journals and academic newspapers, presented in seminars, conferences, classes or other activities with academic purposes, in which the results will only be mentioned in aggregate form and never individually, without any personal and sensitive information. Moreover, in case the datasets are requested by the scientific journal for publication, they will be shared for free, without any information that can identify participants.

3. Interoperability

To ensure the interoperability of the metadata, we will use the DCMI schema

(<https://www.dublincore.org/schemas/>) and the DDI Schema (<https://ddialliance.org/Specification/>).

To ensure the interoperability of the data the preferred file formats for sharing will be *.xls/.xlsx, *.doc/.docx and *.sav (spss), and other formats for physiological data (*.acq, *.raw).

4. Reusability

The processed shared data can be reusable without any restrictions (but only after the publishing of the papers related to the data) and any limit of time. They will be publicly available at the data repository (to be defined later) with license Share-Alike, which allows to (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>):

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format;

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

4. Data security

1. Data recovery processing, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The RAW data collected from both studies through the 2 scales assessment will be stored under the format of an excel file (database) and will be converted in SPSS files and processed (anonymized) for preservation - on the Laboratory PC and cloud storage (NAS). The backups will be done manually. The RAW data collected through EEG will be stored on the harddrives of the Laboratory Netstation PC and backup files in the Laboratory PC “Darwin”, until the end of the data collection period.

The processed data (EEG and physiological data) will be stored on the Laboratory PC and cloud storage, and when necessary on the computers of Tiago Paiva and Catarina Botelho. When necessary, processed data may be stored in Microsoft Teams Software, under a private and password protected channel.

Sensitive and personal data will not be transferred and shared without authorization and additional agreements. They will be stored with minimum access to them and will be destroyed as soon as possible after their processing.

2. Coverage of the ethics review procedure context

The research team already submitted the request of approval to the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto. The submitted documents included a brief description of the project, information regarding ethical issues that may arise during the research (including strategies to lead with them), written consent forms and data collection procedures (questionnaires and brief description of the experimental tasks). After the analysis of the request by the ethics committee, and before the start of the project, the research team will address the necessary adjustments if needed, in order to assure participants safety, comfort, and privacy in all experimental procedures. A similar request will be addressed to the Data Protection Officer of the University of Porto, including a formal request and risk assessment for personal data treatment. Data collection will begin after review and approval by both the Ethics Committee and the Data Protection Officer. More information will be added on the following versions of DMP.

Prior to being conducted, the following steps need to be verified:

1) All participants should be volunteers who agree and assign an informed consent form. Data privacy policies and participants' anonymity will be respected, and data reports will ensure full confidentiality.

2) Questionnaires need to avoid direct questions related to personal and sensitive information. If it is not possible, explain the reason for collecting information of this type.

5. Other matters

Participants' anonymity will be guaranteed during all studies by giving a code to participants. The codification sheet (containing the name, contact information and code of the participants), will be encrypted and stored in the Laboratory PC of Tiago Paiva. Collected data will be stored in three computers - EEG data will be stored in the Laboratory Netstation PC; ECG data in the Laboratory MP36 Data Acquisition Systems (BIOPAC), and self-report data in the Laboratory PC "Darwin". Backup files of EEG and ECGI data will be stored in the Laboratory PC "Darwin". Thus, collected data will not have any subject's personal information.

The DMP will be monitored at least every 6 months. Monitorization will focus on registering the needed changes in all aspects related to the research data management issues. Moreover, it

can also clarify the aspects related to the publication of the datasets on which data repository and their detailed description.

The project website (currently under construction) will be one of the tools to disseminate and communicate results of the studies, addressing targets such as common citizens and the community at large. More information will be added later.

This DMP will be published on Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be citable.

IPR ownership of data produced during the project is from the project team, however, in all communications that refer to project results should mention the collaboration between the team and BIAL has the right to publish and disseminate the results generated under the Project with the authors' acknowledgement.

Regarding dissemination on social networks, the team and BIAL will agree on how the websites or logos will be mentioned and linked. Scientific publications must include the project's reference and the BIAL financing statement.

6. Complementary information

During the project in accordance with the data collection, their processing and analysis the need to create the Data Protection Impact Assessment and collaboration with the Data Protection Officer may emerge. More detailed information about this aspect will be added later in the following versions of the DMP.

The expected data size, licenses and repository for preservation will be defined later and added to Table 1 of the DMP.

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